

MODERN EDUCATION AND ITS ESSENCE

Xolbekova Matluba Abdufattoyevna

Teacher of the faculty of foreign languages of the the Fergane State university

Мамажонова Мунира

English teacher at 23 schools in Tashkent

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12541482>

Abstract

The article discusses modern education as well as its essence

Key words

Innovations in education, new directions of education development, tendencies of modern education development, mission of education

The category of education throughout the history of the development of pedagogical science has been considered from various positions: education as a process, as a result, as a system and as a value. Today, education should be studied from a slightly different angle: education as a component of human culture, as accumulated human capital, as a social good.

The first three positions are quite fully disclosed in the pedagogical literature. Let's focus only on some clarifying points. The first position assumes the development of a person in an educational institution or through self-education of a system of knowledge, skills and abilities, experience of cognitive and practical activities, value orientations and relationships of teachers and students, educators and pupils, their influences and interactions with each other.

The second is the characteristic of the level of achievements of students in the development of knowledge, skills, skills, work experience and relationships. This is the essence of education as a result.

The positions considered indicate that knowledge is in the center of attention as the appropriate results of the spiritual wealth of humanity accumulated by it in historical experience. This approach involves the accumulation of knowledge, the formation of skills and abilities (knowledge to bring it into society. From this point of view, they can be attributed to the human life-support system. At the same time, they absorb the person himself, obscuring his personality. The process of education turns into academism, and knowledge at the same time becomes an absolute value.

In modern conditions, the most relevant is the appeal not to knowledge, skills and abilities, but to competence and competencies. Competence is an integrative personality quality formed on the basis of a set of subject knowledge, skills, and experience reflected in theoretical and applied preparedness for their implementation in activities at the level of functional literacy.

Competence is considered as a synthesis of cognitive, subject-practical and personal experience and as a person's ability to realize competence in a specific practical activity (competence in action). The approach to education as a system presupposes a set of successive educational programs and state educational standards, a network of educational institutions implementing them, and educational management bodies. This is how the concept of "education" is spelled out in the law "On Education". This position can be called managerial. It only regulates what is included in education as a system.

The most difficult is to consider education from the perspective of a value-based approach. Under the influence of the transformation taking place in the country, the functions of education and upbringing are changing, which are becoming much broader and more important than just education, preparing a person for any kind of work. There is an affirmation of a personality-oriented approach, in which education acts as the property of a certain person, as an appropriate value for a particular person. A significant shift in public consciousness is the reorientation of education to new basic values: from ensuring the needs of production and the economy for a certain quality of labor to ensuring the needs of the person himself in obtaining educational services of appropriate quality.

An interesting approach to education as a component of human culture. Culture and education are closely related to each other. It is hardly possible to imagine human life without passing on cultural samples and ways of human interaction with the outside world to subsequent generations. Education is, on the one hand, a means of broadcasting culture, and on the other hand, it itself contributes to the formation of a new culture. There is still an opinion that education and culture are on different sides of the "barricades". An example of this is the fact that the dissertation councils on pedagogical sciences have great difficulty in carrying out works whose topics contain the word "culture". It seems that this approach is insufficiently justified. Education is a priority, and the content of education is one of the factors of economic and social progress of society and should be focused on ensuring self-determination of the individual, creating conditions for his self-realization both personally and professionally. Education is aimed at ensuring that the level of general and professional culture of each individual, the mental development of the individual, his professional qualifications and professional competence are adequate to the world community.

The new interpretation of the category of education in the law "On Education" has led to the possibility to consider it not only from the perspective of personality-oriented education, but also from the perspective of a person-centered approach.

In the conditions of rapid development of society, education acts as accumulated human capital, which can be realized in subsequent life. From the perspective of this approach, the category of education has a pronounced social aspect. It seems that it is advisable to consider education from the perspective of the unity of education, upbringing and training as the main categories of pedagogical science. In this case, education and training can be perceived as two interrelated and conditioned sides of a single category of "education". Achievements in each component are assessed through the levels of education and upbringing.

The idea of continuous human development as a subject of activity is recognized as the central idea of education. The understanding of development as a continuous process should be combined with the principle of developmental learning, the orientation of educational activities not only to cognition of the world, but also its transformation. This is the reason for the transition to an open education system. Openness as a new condition for the functioning of the modern vocational education system in Uzbekistan presupposes its broad interaction with society, organic involvement in market relations with recognition of the priority of customers (employers) for personnel training.

The priority tasks of education include the formation in the minds of the younger generation of a scientific picture of the world – natural, social, personal, a picture that would reflect objective reality most fully and deeply. Today's world is, first of all, the humanization and democratization of interpersonal relations. These are new forms of communication, new forms of contacts between people and fostering a tolerant attitude towards other peoples. The pedagogical problem, whatever it may be, is fraught with universal humanity in the sense that it has a universal character and is of common value to all peoples of the world.

A society in constant development, through education, puts forward to a person and implements through him new requirements related to the trends and contradictions of the new XXI century. The main ones include:

learning ability, i.e. the ability of a person to constantly improve the level of knowledge, to master new types of activities, including professional ones; intellectual and physical development, ensuring success in mastering new

technologies and maintaining health; creativity, i.e. the ability to think and act creatively not only in the educational process, but also in future professional activity;

The state of modern education is characterized by a change in pedagogical paradigms. New systems, technologies, and approaches emerging in modern education give rise to a new psychological and pedagogical attitude to the learning process, which has been called innovative. Innovative processes are innovations in education, the introduction of new content and new methods with different properties associated with a change in semantic guidelines.

Among the innovative pedagogical processes, the following should be highlighted:

- implementation of the transition of a mass school to a new basic curriculum, including federal, regional and school components, variable programs, teaching and upbringing methods demanded by the new living conditions of society;
 - the emergence of original concepts and new models of schools, lyceums, colleges and gymnasiums;
 - development of federal and regional educational development programs that take into account the socio-economic, cultural and ethnic characteristics of the subjects;
 - active updating of the content of general secondary and vocational education based on the ideas of humanization and humanitarization;
 - Ensuring the continuity of professional education;
 - restructuring of organizational forms, methods of education and upbringing, taking into account personality-oriented and personality-centered approaches;
 - Integration of primary and secondary vocational education in connection with the changing forms of ownership in the State;
 - transition of educational institutions from the mode of functioning to the mode of sustainable development;
 - creation of diagnostic services in educational institutions (psychological, valeological, sociological, etc.);
 - quality management of education on a diagnostic basis;
 - implementation of a continuous process of professional development of teaching staff;

The pan-European trend of "lifelong learning" has been formulated and adopted for leadership in countries with developed market economies. Since our

country has also embarked on this path, the experience of market countries needs to be analyzed and used. Such key ideas of the principle of "lifelong learning" as basic skills for everyone, more investment in human resources, the value of education, rethinking approaches to the upbringing of the younger generation.

Currently, there is a change in the educational paradigm. The main contradiction of the modern education system is between the rapid rate of increment of knowledge in the modern world and the limited possibilities of their assimilation by an individual. This contradiction forces pedagogical theory to abandon the absolute educational ideal (a comprehensively developed personality) and move on to a new ideal – the maximum development of human abilities, self-regulation and self-education. The modernization of the country is based on the modernization of education, on its substantial and structural renewal. It is necessary to do everything possible to ensure the resource provision of the educational sphere. However, resources should be directed not to the conservation of the system, but to its effective updating.

Speaking about the problems of modern education, it is impossible to consider it in isolation from global trends. However, they are overlaid with a number of features related to the crisis socio-economic situation, the rejection of previous values, and ongoing socio-cultural changes. The task of education in the 21st century is to overcome the crisis of culture, spirituality and humanism.

Educational policy, as V.I. Zagvyazinsky points out, should take into account social, content-oriented, process-oriented and personality-oriented orientations [2].

Social orientation. Priority is given to social requirements for a person as a citizen, a worker, a member of society, his qualities and abilities. Education is becoming one of the crucial values of life. The content-oriented orientation is determined by the increased demands of the world community for the knowledge, skills and abilities acquired in connection with the new level of production, science and culture. Educational systems are becoming designed to train specialists of a high level of professional qualification.

A process-oriented orientation. In this case, preference is given to the learning process itself, educational technologies, teaching methods and teaching methods, joint activities of the student and the teacher.

A personality-oriented orientation is expressed in the unconditional priority of the interests of a developing personality and is realized through a personality-oriented technology of education and upbringing. So, a new

pedagogy is being built, which is based on the idea of humanism, its parity, recognition of the highest value – human life and life in general.

The main trends and directions of development of modern education include such as globalization, fundamentalization, humanization, technologization, standardization, computerization. Let's take a closer look at the identified trends in modern education. The globalization of education is determined primarily by the fact that education and society are inseparable from each other. And this still has to be proved from the position of the priority importance of the development of education for human civilization, for a single person. The field of education is designed to adjust its priorities and values taking into account not only relevant, but also promising, long-term needs of both man and society, it works for the future, "predetermining the personal qualities of each person, his knowledge, skills, ideological and behavioral priorities," B.S. notes. Gershunsky [3, p. 20]. A single world market, a single information space, and the integration of local civilizations into a single global community ensure the reproduction of social ties and relations in historical space and time. The unified history of mankind, which has absorbed the experience of all peoples, has led to the emergence of one of the most important problems of mankind – survival. Globalization is becoming a common destiny for peoples and cultures, who, in order to preserve themselves, must come to understand the increased responsibility of man and humanity for life and its quality. Maybe, being on the brink of death, humanity will finally stop the destructive forces and begin to return to the true values of life.

Education should be fundamental, i.e. deep and thorough. The recognition of fundamentalization is caused by an increase in the volume of information, its updating every 2-3 years. The primary tasks in this area are: the introduction of a cycle of general humanities disciplines in natural science and technical education in order to overcome the disunity of natural science and humanitarian components of a holistic ideological culture of the individual; creation of integrated interdisciplinary courses that contain the most universal and generalized knowledge, which are the basis of applied research and development, the basis for the formation of a general and professional culture of the individual, rapid adaptation to new professions and specialties; overcoming the contradiction between fundamental education and vocational training with the unconditional priority of fundamental knowledge.

The humanitarization of education concerns the issues of education, upbringing and personal development of students, as well as issues of its

organization, functioning and management. It is assumed that it should be implemented throughout the education system, penetrating the humanitarian and natural science components of education, the field of technical, engineering, economic and other sciences.

Humanitarization is a particular manifestation of a common task related to the revival of culturally related education. To humanize education means to identify the personal meaning in the study of educational disciplines of both the humanities and natural sciences, to realize its significance from the perspective of each individual, i.e. to make it personally oriented and personally significant. Let's turn to the history of the issue under consideration. Her study and analysis of modern international trends in the humanitarization of education make it possible to clarify the essence of the matter in many ways. Natural science was originally humanitarian: it is the basis of people's worldview.

Currently, the tasks of reorganizing higher education, transferring it to the mode of innovative development, ensuring the full-fledged entry of the country into a post-industrial, information society, are acute. The system of higher professional education is entering a new phase of its functioning, as there is a transition from specialist training to education and formation of a person's personality, which, in turn, requires the development and real implementation in practice of a new educational paradigm of education and training aimed at a particular person.

Literature:

1. Смирнов, И.П. Новый принцип воспитания: ориентация на интересы молодежи / И.П. Смирнов, Е.В. Ткаченко. – М., 2005.
2. Загвязинский, В.И. Теория обучения: современная интерпретация : учеб. пособие для студентов высш. пед. учеб. заведений / В.И. Загвязинский. – М., 2001.
- Research in Innovative Teaching and Inclusive Learning, 1(2), 1-5.
3. Abdufattoyevna, H. M. (2023). Teaching English to Low Proficiency Students. American Journal of Science on Integration and Human Development (2993-2750), 1(7), 30-36.
4. Abdufattoyevna, H. M. (2023). Teaching English to Low Proficiency Students. American Journal of Science on Integration and Human Development (2993-2750), 1(7), 30-36.
5. Abdufattoyevna, H. M. (2023). The Role of Communication in Language Learning. Best Journal of Innovation in Science, Research and Development, 2(6), 55-60.

6. Abdufattoyevna, H. M. (2023). The Role of Communication in Language Learning. *Best Journal of Innovation in Science, Research and Development*, 2(6), 55-60.
7. Abdufattoyevna, H. M. (2023). TEACHING ENGLISH AS THE SECOND FOREIGN LANGUAGE. *BARQARORLIK VA YETAKCHI TADQIQOTLAR ONLAYN ILMIY JURNALI*, 3(4), 21-27.
8. Холбекова, М. А., & Холбекова, Д. (2023). IQTISODIYOTNING RIVOJLANISHIDA CHET TILLARINI O'QITISHNING AHAMIYATI. *Journal of Universal Science Research*, 1(5), 472-478.
9. Abdufattoyevna, H. M. (2023). Teaching English to Low Proficiency Students. *American Journal of Science on Integration and Human Development (2993-2750)*, 1(7), 30-36.
10. Umirov, S. B. (2023). NATIONAL STRUGGLE AS ONE OF THE TYPES OF PHYSICAL CULTURE. *American Journal of Pedagogical and Educational Research*, 18, 133-137.
11. Umirov, S. B. (2021). Kurashchilar jismoniy fazilatlarni rivojlantirish. *Scientific progress*, 2(8), 41-46.
12. Umirov, S. B. (2023). NATIONAL STRUGGLE AS ONE OF THE TYPES OF PHYSICAL CULTURE. *American Journal of Pedagogical and Educational Research*, 18, 133-137.
13. 8. Холбекова, М. А., & Холбекова, Д. (2023). IQTISODIYOTNING RIVOJLANISHIDA CHET TILLARINI O'QITISHNING AHAMIYATI. *Journal of Universal Science Research*, 1(5), 472-478.
14. Abdufattoyevna, H. M. (2023). Teaching English to Low Proficiency Students. *American Journal of Science on Integration and Human Development (2993-2750)*, 1(7), 30-36.
15. Umirov, S. B. (2023). NATIONAL STRUGGLE AS ONE OF THE TYPES OF PHYSICAL CULTURE. *American Journal of Pedagogical and Educational Research*, 18, 133-137.
16. Alisher o'g'li, A. N., & Ilkhomovich, A. B. (2022). THE ROLE OF NATIONAL GAMES AND THE FAMILY, SCHOOL AND COMMUNITY IN THE SPIRITUAL UPBRINGING OF CHILDREN. *Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal*, 10(3), 625-627.